

THE IMPORTANCE OF QUICK SPEECH IN IMPROVING ACTOR'S SPEECH TECHNIQUE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of sound, speech and stage speech in cinema, theater and television and radio, and what to focus on to develop pure pronunciation and speech.*

Keywords: *art, speech, stage speech, theater, radio, articulation, sound, orthoepy.*

It is well known that theatrical art is a syncretic-mixed art, that is, it includes other types of art, but at the same time, theater without actors is inanimate. An actor is a creator through words and speech. "If an actor is the king of theatrical art, the crown on his head is the art of speech," says director Donchenko Nemirovich. The actor has the task of translating the written text created by the author into an oral speech.

In order for an actor to master stage speech skills, he or she will need to constantly follow them in order to master the components of interrelated but dissimilar, yet complementary, speech techniques. These are as follows.

- Articulation
- Diction
- Breath
- Sound
- Orpheus

The means of elevating the art of live speech, more precisely, the simple word to the level of high art, fine art, are the oral cavity, lips, teeth, which are the sources of sound, breath, and pronunciation. consists of a number of body parts such as the tongue, nasal passages, reflectors, throat, vocal cords, lung air cavities, and the diaphragm.

Each member of the performer who demonstrates the art of real stage speech, in particular the speech organs, is consciously subordinated to him and, if necessary, tuned to the desired tone and note. In order to achieve such perfection, humanity has a system of physical and psychological exercises, developed in the course of its

historical development and, in particular, the gradual development of art, tested in practice and recognized worldwide, which we have mentioned above in the language of art. Called “speech technique”.

One of the main factors in the art of acting is the word, talent, quality, skill, sophistication, courage, courage. We believe that solutions can be found in our lives and in our various creative processes through rational thought, the power of words, and wisdom.

In the art of acting, the endless possibilities of our verbal behavior and artistic expression must be constantly strengthened and complicated. In keeping with the times, we strive to pay more attention to its burdens, pains, joys and sorrows, its main purpose, to strengthen the leading, moving, life-giving power of language, which reflects the philosophy of the time. In theater, film, pop, radio and television, it is necessary to make extensive use of the power of speech, artistic expression, inspiring, convincing, enlarging, spiritual, convincing. We need to connect the principles of speech, its ideological and educational functions with the times. Because the responsibility of our future, the education of creative actors, directors, masters of words, speakers, orators who can carry the burden, is the most effective of our tasks.

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